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Ibadova Nafisa AxmatilloeyvnaSamarkand state institute of foreign languages,
senior teacher, Independent researcher**THE ROLE OF KHALED HOSSEINI'S CREATIVITY IN THE FORMATION OF THE
LITERARY CULTURE OF CENTRAL ASIA** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10157536>**ANNOTATION**

In this article is discussed the role of the Afghan writer Khaled Hosseini, who lived and worked in America, in the world of literature, the features of the coverage of the literary culture of Central Asia. If we talk about the countries of Central Asia, then it is not only Afghanistan, but also Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and a number of other countries. It is necessary to study the most valuable monuments of the material and spiritual culture of these regions, majestic architectural structures, sculptural images, wall paintings, unique manuscripts and form the basis of the priority tasks facing us, the younger generations.

Key words: literary heritage, mentality, Khaled Hosseini, Central Asia, cultural heritage, creativity, monument, nationality, value.

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КУЛЬТУРЫ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В данной статье рассматривается роль афганского писателя Халеда Хоссейни, жившего и творившего в Америке, в мировой литературе, особенности освещения литературной культуры Центральной Азии. Если говорить о странах Центральной Азии, то это не только Афганистан, но и Кыргызстан, Узбекистан, Таджикистан и ряд других стран. Необходимо изучить ценнейшие памятники материальной и духовной культуры этих регионов, величественные архитектурные сооружения, скульптурные изображения, настенные росписи, уникальные рукописи и составить основу приоритетных задач, стоящих перед нами, подрастающими поколениями.

Ключевые слова: литературное наследие, менталитет, Халед Хоссейни, Центральная Азия, культурное наследие, творчество, памятник, национальность, ценность.

Ibadova Nafisa Axmatilloeyvna
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katta o'qituvchi, Mustaqil tadqiqotchi

O'RTA OSIYO ADABIY MADANIYATINING SHAKLLANISHIDA XALID HUSAYNIY IJODINING O'RNI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Amerikada yashab ijod qilgan afg'on yozuvchisi Xolid Husayniyning adabiyot olamidagi o'rni, Markaziy Osiyo adabiy madaniyatini yoritish xususiyatlari haqida so'z boradi. Agar Markaziy Osiyo davlatlari haqida gapiradigan bo'lsak, bu nafaqat Afg'oniston, balki Qirg'iziston, O'zbekiston, Tojikiston va boshqa bir qator davlatlardir. Bu hududlarning moddiy va ma'naviy madaniyatining eng qimmat yodgorliklari, mahobatli me'moriy inshootlari, haykaltaroshlik timsollari, devoriy suratlar, noyob qo'lyozmalarni chuqur o'rganish va biz, yosh avlod oldida turgan ustuvor vazifalarning asosini tashkil etish zarur.

Kalit so'zlar: adabiy meros, mentalitet, Xolid Husayniy, Markaziy Osiyo, madaniy meros, ijod, yodgorlik, millat, qadriyat

INTRODUCTION:

We know that the people, nations and folks of the world have a rich literary heritage, testifying to their history, origin, development, progress, they know about the past of their ancestors who lived and settled on the territory of Central Asia. It deserves special attention because it has a rich cultural heritage, rooted in antiquity. Such information comes to us through the most valuable monuments of material and spiritual culture, majestic architectural structures, sculptural images, murals, unique manuscripts found by scientists from Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and other nearby regions[7].

The development of the culture of each society occurs on the basis of continuity, reflecting its material conditions and socio-economic needs. The culture of any society can really develop only on the basis of the cultural achievements of the past. Each society does not create everything from scratch, but uses ready-made values of material and spiritual culture. There are many examples of this from history, because it would not be an exaggeration to say that they have already been confirmed.

MAIN PART

In the process of writing this short research paper, we have studied the work of many researchers and used their rich and meaningful results. Based on their information, we can say that although different peoples live in Central Asia, they are distinguished by many common points in life and way of thinking, but there is no difference between the inhabitants of these countries at all (except for appearance and language)[6]. We can draw such valuable and important information from the works of researchers and the works of the Afghan writer and physician Khaled Hosseini.

In the main part of this article, we considered it permissible to touch briefly on the life and work of Khaled Hosseini. The works of Khaled Hosseini, who was originally born in Afghanistan and lived in America by the will of fate, created 3 world-famous works telling about the past and present life of Central Asia, especially Afghanistan, and the sad fate of its women: "Thousands of Solar Lights", "Running for wind", "Mountains also sounded" entered the minds and hearts of readers by taking their place in the world of literature, becoming popular bestsellers, different from the works of other writers. It is interesting to be close to the reader. The bloody wars that have been going on in Afghanistan for several decades have changed the fate of millions of people, so that the words about a beautiful life have become a dream for them. Khaled Hosseini, who witnessed such wars, vividly embodied what he saw and experienced, the events that shook his heart in the images of his heroes[10].

The region of Central Asia differs from other regions in having a rich and colorful culture with different ethnic groups, languages and traditions. His literature reflects the specific features of the peoples of the region, including their mentality, experience, beliefs, worldview. Here, some features of the literary tradition of Central Asia are especially important, and we considered it

appropriate to mention them. First, oral tradition occupies a special place in literature. We know from history that there is a strong tradition of oral storytelling in the literary genre of Central Asia. Folk tales, legends, songs and epics are often passed down from generation to generation and have a great influence on the literary heritage of the country.

The next feature can be called the influence of Islam. This religion has had a significant presence in Central Asia since the 8th century and its teachings have had a strong influence on the literature of the region. Islamic themes, values and symbols can be found in many works of Central Asian literature, especially in regional poetry[1].

The next feature is works related to love and romantic relationships. We present them in different forms, for example: in many works of Central Asian literature, romantic themes are often explored by writers about marriages of convenience and other traditional forms of dating[5]. When determining the conditions for the emergence of the culture of the peoples of Central Asia, it is necessary to pay attention to its geographical location and natural resources. In general, Central Asian literature reflects a rich and diverse cultural heritage, focusing on storytelling, Islamic influence, nomadic traditions, respect for elders, love, and romance[4].

The book "Ancient Civilization" shows two features of the culture of Central Asia: on the one hand, its development due to the interaction of different cultures, and on the other hand, its development in close contact with other centers of ancient civilizations. If we take a closer look at these features, the processes of formation of the culture of Central Asia will be clearly visible[6].

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

Only the way of life, worldview, features and concepts in the names of things and objects differ from other peoples. Such features distinguish the way of thinking, behavior, clothing, food, traditions and other specific features of this people from other peoples. As a result, there are words expressing various concepts that belong only to this people, and the concepts that these words designate do not exist in the language of other peoples.

At this stage, we will focus on the coverage of Central Asia, especially Afghan culture, in the works of Khaled Hosseini. Studying the works of the writer, we will have the opportunity to get acquainted with the geographical location, nature, nationality and culture, language and customs of the country and Afghan society. Unlike neighboring countries, Afghanistan is not a century, but a decade of societal violence, structural disorder, and disorder. The country is divided into three regions: Northern Plains, Central Landmarks and Southern Plains. Most of the northern plains used to be used for agriculture, but as a result of droughts and wars, most of the plains were destroyed. Thus, Afghanistan is considered a third world country mainly because of its geographical location and history of wars. The work depicts the city centers of Kabul, Afghanistan. In this example, how different the situation is between the streets and central cities of Kabul and the outlying villages of Afghanistan can be seen from the description of Nana's house in the outlying village and the area where Maryam's father lives.

It was Muhsin, Jalil's eldest son by his first wife, Khadija, who suggested the clearing. It was on the outskirts of Gul Daman. To get to it, one took a rutted, uphill dirt track that branched off the main road between Herat and Gul Daman. The track was flanked on either side by knee-high grass and speckles of white and bright yellow flowers. The track snaked uphill and led to a flat field where poplars and cottonwoods soared and wild bushes grew in clusters. From up there, one could make out the tips of the rusted blades of Gul Daman's windmill, on the left, and, on the right, all of Herat spread below. The path ended perpendicular to a wide, trout-filled stream, which rolled down from the Safidkoh mountains surrounding Gul Daman. Two hundred yards upstream, toward the mountains, there was a circular grove of weeping willow trees. In the center, in the shade of the willows, was the clearing. The example above describes the nature of the remote villages of Afghan society.

Afghan culture consistently exhibits a patriarchal despotism in which women are dependent on their husbands and especially boys, and male children are the only way to gain social status. We can show the fate of Aziza and Zalmay, the children of Rashid and Layla, in Huayni's Thousand Suns. Due to not very good family conditions, they send their eldest daughter Aziza to an orphanage. But Zalmay treats his sons very highly, and all his wishes will be fulfilled. Maybe if Aziza had been a boy,

he would not have been sent to an orphanage. Even when she was born, there was no great joy, that is, there was no great joy in Afghan families when a girl was born.

We know that some people have a way of life, worldview, features and concepts in the names of things and objects that differ from those of other peoples. Such features distinguish the way of thinking, behavior, clothing, food, traditions and other specific features of this nation from other peoples. As a result, there are words expressing various concepts that belong only to this people, and the concepts that these words designate do not exist in the language of other peoples. If you look at it from this point of view, then in the works of Khaled Hosseini, the features of the life of the peoples of Central Asia are described intelligibly and skillfully, which awakens the reader's imagination and, in the necessary places.[2].

In this passage, used in the writings of Khaled Hosseini: "You want to come with my family," the young man said "I know it's zahmat for you. But you look like a decent brother, and I-" "Don't worry, hamshira I understand. It's no trouble. Let me go and buy your tickets."

"Thank you, brother. This is sawab, a good deed. God will remember"[3].

The above passage also used words denoting nationality, culture. This passage uses words such as "hard work", "nurse", "reward", which in English means the same as words such as "hard work", "nurse", "good death". This helped shed light on a culture based on concrete realities. We know that it is very important for Muslims to do good deeds, to help someone, and this is called a reward. Doing good deeds is the duty of every Muslim. It can be seen from this that the use of this word also reflected the original national culture.

CONCLUSION

In this article, the story based on national culture is based on the book "A Thousand Rays of the Sun", which is considered by one of the American Afghan writers Khaled Hosseini, which tells about the way of life, culture and traditions of Central Asia, especially the Afghan land and its surrounding regions. We tried shed light on developments. In the work "A Thousand Suns" he skillfully used the realities of written national culture and effectively used them to describe the following national features.

Finally, we can say that those who studied the writer's work can easily enjoy the rich literary, spiritual and material life of people who lived in Central Asia. The value of the writer's works lies in the fact that they are covered convincingly, simply and comprehensively. He skillfully used words to express nationality. In his works, he used such national costumes as capes, cloaks, hijabs, apakol as realities. Through these concepts, the reader not only helps to visualize the Afghan women's and men's costumes, but also allows you to get acquainted with their national costumes. The nationality and culture of this people are embodied in the eyes of the reader who has read the writer's works.

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